

Actualization of the Great Commission in Christian Religion Based On the Gospel (Matthew 28:19-20)

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Abstract: The great commission is an important part of Christian or church life. One of the factors for church growth (quantitatively) is carrying out the great commission. A church that carries out the great commission is a dynamic church that continues to grow and develop. Apart from that, the great commission is the essence of the church's duties and calling in the world which must not be ignored. This is a task that cannot be rejected by all Christians, including a Christian Religious Counselor because it is in accordance with his nature, namely a mandate that comes from Jesus. The research method used in this journal article is the library *genesis* method, namely a method of collecting data by understanding and studying theories related to finding sources and constructing them from various sources such as books, articles, journals that have already been carried out. . A Christian religious instructor is someone who is given the task, responsibility and authority by authorized officials to carry out religious guidance and development counseling using the language of the Christian religion. The mandate of the Lord Jesus is called the Great Commission because the Giver of the mandate is the Holder of the Supreme Authority in this universe. Apart from that, this mandate is called the Great Commission because its reach is all nations (the whole world). The concept of the great commission in Matthew 28:19-20 with a foreground that is different from what existed in the past, which became the background of the passage. Jesus' words in the early days of AD civilization do not always have to be understood as they were in his time, because every event and text cannot be separated from the context that surrounds it.

Keywords: *Religious instructor, Great Commission.*

Introduction

The great commission is an important part of Christian or church life. One of the factors for church growth (quantitatively) is carrying out the great commission. A church that carries out the great commission is a dynamic church that continues to grow and develop. Apart from that, the great commission is the essence of the church's duties and calling in the world which must not be ignored. This is a task that cannot be rejected by all Christians, including a Christian Religious Counselor because it is in accordance with his nature, namely a mandate that comes from Jesus.

Draw closer to God as a form of surrender to their current situation.¹ Spiritually directs humans to gain experience subjectively so that they not only understand what life is but also why they live.² Therefore, human spirituality must be continuously improved so that it is of higher quality.

The problems in the elderly are decreased physical ability, decreased activity, and often experience health problems, all of which cause them to lose enthusiasm. The effect of this condition of decreasing physical ability causes those who are elderly to feel worthless or underappreciated. According to Rita Arkinson's research results cited by Jalaluddin, it was found that the main problem faced by the elderly is an inner conflict between wholeness and hopelessness.³ Therefore, they tend to remember past successes, so those who are older like to help active teenagers, especially in religious activities. The religious problems faced by humans of all ages are not much different. This means that what is a problem for older people can also be a problem for young people. According to Aunur Rahim Faqih, human religious problems can be broken down as follows: 1) Problems occur because of non-religion; meaning that a person or group of people has no religion or has no religion and wishes to embrace a religion, finds it difficult to embrace or adhere to a religion because they have not been able to convince themselves which religion is most appropriate for them to adhere to. 2) Problems occur because of the choice of religion; That is, a person or group of people who do not yet adhere to a religion and want to embrace a religion find it

¹ Britani, C. W., Ranimpi, Y. Y., & Nusawakan, A. W. *Elderly Spiritual Health in Getasan and Orphanages Wredha White Cross of Salatiga*. 2018. 13(2), 12. Link <https://doi.org/10.31983/link.v13i2.284>

² Haqiqi Rafsanjani. *Spiritual Leadership (Spiritual Leadership)*. Journal of Masharif Al-Syariah: Journal of Economics And Sharia Banking. 2021. 2(1)

³ Jalaluddin Rakhmat, *Social Psychology*, Youth Rosdakarya: Jakarta. (2000)

difficult to choose a particular religion to follow. 3) Problems occur because of shaky faith; which means a person or group of individuals who always waver in their beliefs, so there is a tendency at one time to follow one religion, and at another to want to follow another. 4) Problems occur because of differences in understanding and views; meaning that a person or group of individuals suffers from inner conflict because they receive conflicting information about beliefs and culture that makes it difficult for them to carry out an action or deed. 5) problems occur due to misunderstanding of religion teach which things; which means a person or group of people commits an action or deed that consciously or not harms himself and/or others, due to a lack of understanding of religious teachings. 6) Problems occur because of the implementation of religious teachings; This means that a person or group of people cannot carry out religious teachings as they should for various reasons.⁴

The spiritual quality of everyone must be different depending on the level of one's worship. Mature spiritual development will help humans face the reality of playing an active role in life and formulating the meaning and purpose of their existence in life. The elderly is the final stage of the human life cycle that cannot be avoided and will be experienced by every long-lived individual.⁵ WHO states that the elderly is divided into four groups, namely middle age (45-59 years), elderly (60-74 years), old (75-90 years), and very old (very old). more than 90 years. According to Setyonegoro, the elderly (Germanic age) is divided into 3 age boundaries, namely young old (age 70-75 years), old (age 75-80 years), and very old (age > 80 years).⁶ Based on the statement above, the elderly is classified as an age that requires special attention both in terms of physical and spiritual health.⁷

As explained by Hurlock there are several characteristics of the elderly, namely: a) Old age is a period of decline; The decline in the elderly comes partly from physical factors and psychological factors. Setbacks can have an impact on the psychology of the elderly. Motivation has an important role in the decline of the elderly. The decline in the elderly is faster if they have low motivation, conversely, if they have strong motivation, the setback will take a long time to occur. b) The elderly is a minority group; The elderly has the status of a minority group as a result of unpleasant social attitudes towards the elderly reinforced by bad clichéd opinions towards the elderly. This cliché opinion is like the elderly prefer to defend their opinions rather than listen to the opinions of others. c) Aging requires a change of roles. This role change was made because the elderly began to experience setbacks in all respects. Changes in the role of the elderly should be done based on their desires, not based on pressure from the environment. d) Poor adjustment in the elderly. Poor treatment of the elderly makes the elderly tend to develop a poor self-concept. Older

people show more forms of bad behavior. Because of this mistreatment, the adjustment of the elderly is worse.⁸

The government's efforts to care for the elderly in Indonesia have been quite good, for example by coordinating the existence of an elderly POSYANDU in every village. In addition to treating the elderly from a physical health perspective, it is also supported from a spiritual health perspective which is shown in religious activities by their respective religions.⁹ Because it greatly affects the quality of life of the elderly. In addition, the elderly also lives happily without depression, so they can live a healthy life. Spiritual strengthening of the elderly can minimize the occurrence of depression in the elderly. Based on the existing theory, depression is one of the psychological problems experienced by the elderly. Therefore, spiritual strengthening can be an effective tool for preventing depression. The elderly can still be developed and improved spiritually even though biologically, genetically, physically, and socially experience many declines. However, it is different from other aspects, the spirituality of the elderly can be continuously improved and improved as they get older.¹⁰

Several methods can be used in outreach to the elderly, namely: 1) The discussion method is a teaching method in which the teacher gives a problem (problem) to students, and students are allowed to jointly solve this problem with their friends.¹¹ 2) the lecture method, namely the delivery of lessons carried out by the teacher with oral narratives or direct explanations in front of students.¹² 3) The question and answer method is a method in which the teacher uses/gives statements to students and students answer, or vice versa students ask the teacher and the teacher answers student questions.¹³ 4) Reinforcement method is a positive response to strengthen and motivate a person to accept himself, this method can be done verbally or nonverbally. So, the authors study that the most suitable technique used in educating the elderly while in the field is the reinforcement method.

DISCUSSION

Methods of Providing Strengthening and Guidance Techniques for Christian Religion Teachers

Reinforcement is a response to a behavior that increases the likelihood of the behavior recurring. In terms of counseling, known as positive reinforcement and negative reinforcement. Positive reinforcement is reinforcement that aims to maintain and maintain

⁴ Aunur Rahim Faqih, (2001), *Guidance and Counseling in Islam*, UUI Press: Jogjakarta

⁵ Widyastuti, R. H. (2014). *Differences in Everyday Spiritual Experience in the Elderly in Nursing Homes and in Public*. Journal of Community Nursing, 2(2), 64–69.

⁶ Naftali, A. R., Ranimpi, Y. Y., & Anwar, M. A. (2017). *Spiritual Health and Elderly Preparedness in Facing Death*. Psychology Bulletin, 25(2), 124–135. <https://doi.org/10.22146/buletinsikologi.28992>

⁷ Nababan, A. (2020). *Christian parents' democratic parenting patterns in Shaping Teenager's Character*. Jurnal Dinamika Pendidikan, 13 (2), 127-134. <https://doi.org/10.51212/jdp.v13i2.1584>

⁸ Hurlock, 1999. *Developmental Psychology: The Life Span Approach*. Fifth edition (Translation by Istiwidayanti). Jakarta: Erlangga.hal.189.

⁹ Sakirman, S. (2019). *Elderly Socio-Religious Development in Building Social Piety Constructs*. Development Innovation: Research Journal,7(2), 157. <https://doi.org/10.35450/jip.v7i2.138>

¹⁰ Santika, Adhi, Turana, N. A. (2013). *Overview of Elderly Health in Indonesia*. The Ambassador and Health Information Window Bulletin, 1–32.

¹¹ Soetomo, *Definition of Discussion Method*. (1993), <https://repository.uir.ac.id/2217/3/BAB%20II.pdf> accessed on 20 March 2022.

¹² Abuddin. *Lecture Method Analysis*. (2014). [https://jurnal.fipps.ikipgriptk.ac.id/index.php/SEJARAH/article/download/62/pdf#:~:text=strategi%20pembelajaran%20ekspositori,Menuurut%20Abuddin%20Nata%20\(dalam%20Tambak%2C%202014%3A377\)%20metode,langsung%20di%20hadapan%20peserta%20didik](https://jurnal.fipps.ikipgriptk.ac.id/index.php/SEJARAH/article/download/62/pdf#:~:text=strategi%20pembelajaran%20ekspositori,Menuurut%20Abuddin%20Nata%20(dalam%20Tambak%2C%202014%3A377)%20metode,langsung%20di%20hadapan%20peserta%20didik) accessed on 20 March 2022.

¹³ J.J.Hasibuan, Moedjiono. *Definition of Question and Answer Method*. (2010). <https://repository.uir.ac.id/3397/5/bab2.pdf> accessed on 20 March 2022.

positive behavior, while negative reinforcement is strengthening behavior by stopping or removing unpleasant stimuli.¹⁴

The following is the definition and meaning of reinforcement from several book sources: a) According to Usman (2008), reinforcement is any form of response that is verbal or nonverbal, which is part of the teacher's behavior modification of student behavior, which aims to provide information or feedback to recipients (students) for his actions as an act of encouragement or correction. b) According to Putra (2005), reinforcement is a response given to students for behavior or actions that are considered good, which can lead to repetition or improvement of actions or behavior that are considered good. c) According to Prayitno (2009), reinforcement is an effort by educators to strengthen, stabilize, or affirm certain things that exist in students. What is strengthened is none other than the positive things that exist in students, especially positive behavior which is the result of changes due to students' self-development efforts. d) According to Barnawi and Arifin (2012), reinforcement is a positive response in learning given by the teacher to positive student behavior with the aim of maintaining and increasing this behavior. e) According to Soemanto (2006), reinforcement is a positive response from the teacher to students who have done good deeds or achievements. Giving reinforcement is carried out by the teacher with the aim that students can more actively participate in teaching and learning interactions and students can repeat these good deeds.¹⁵

So according to the author that the reinforcement method is a positive response to be able to strengthen and motivate someone to accept himself, this method can be done verbally or nonverbally whereas the verbal method is a method that can be done in the form of encouragement, praise, and recognition in strengthening the elderly while Non-verbal methods are usually used through body language, facial expressions, gestures or other actions such as shaking your head or giving a thumbs up.

According to Skinner, reinforcement is generally divided into two types, namely: 1) Positive reinforcement, namely reinforcement based on the principle that the frequency of responses increases because it is followed by a supporting stimulus (reward). Forms of positive reinforcement in the form of prizes (candy, parcels, food, etc.), behavior (smiling, nodding your head in agreement, clapping, giving thumbs up), or awards (grade A, 1st place, and so on). 2) Negative reinforcement, is reinforcement based on the principle that the frequency of the response increases because it is followed by the removal of an adverse (unpleasant) stimulus. Forms of negative reinforcement include: delaying/not rewarding, giving additional tasks, or showing displeased behavior (trembling, frowning, disappointed face, etc.).¹⁶

Principles of Giving Reinforcement: a) Warmth and enthusiasm. The reinforcement given should be accompanied by warmth and enthusiasm. Warmth and enthusiasm can be shown in

various ways, for example by a beaming face/face accompanied by a smile, a cheerful voice full of concern, or a gesture that gives the impression that the reinforcement given is genuine. b) Meaningfulness. The reinforcement provided by the instructor must be meaningful to the client. That is, the client does feel compelled to improve his appearance. c) Avoid using negative feedback. Negative responses such as harsh words, insults, punishments, or ridicule from extension workers are powerful weapons to destroy the conducive atmosphere and personality of the client itself. Therefore, extension workers should avoid all kinds of negative feedback.¹⁷

METHODS AND TECHNIQUES FOR STRENGTHENING

Techniques for giving reinforcement are divided into 2, namely verbal and non-verbal. verbally, namely comments in the form of praise, recognition, and encouragement used to strengthen the behavior of the elderly. Non-verbally, namely a) reinforcement in the form of gestures and body movements such as smiles, nods and sometimes accompanied by verbal reinforcement b) reinforcement with approaches, namely approaching extension workers to the elderly to express concern and enjoyment of the work or behavior of the elderly c) reinforcement with touch d) reinforcement by doing fun activities.

The method that we will use in counseling the elderly is group strengthening, namely giving reinforcement to all group members can be done continuously as well as giving reinforcement to individuals. Verbal, gestural, cue, and reinforcement activities are components of reinforcement that can be given to all group members.

In this case, spiritual activities will be carried out for the elderly. Service activities are as follows: a) Bible reading activities b) Lecture activities with the theme of healthy faith. c) Give good and correct advice, advice, appeals, and invitations. In counseling, counselors use more verbal, namely in the form of questions that must be answered by the client properly, honestly, and correctly. For the counselor to get honest and open answers and questions from the client, the sentences the counselor utters must be words that are easy to understand, polite, and do not offend or hurt the client's feelings. Likewise, when giving advice or positive views on matters that the client should contemplate, it should be done in beautiful, friendly, reassuring, and pleasant sentences. d) Read a prayer for the client. To stabilize the client, the prayer said by the counselor must be heard by the client or his soul becomes calm and also says the word "amen". This technique can be done by counselors in group counseling. This technique is also very beneficial for clients because prayer can generate optimism and peace of mind. Religious activities for the elderly are expected to increase and strengthen their spirituality of the elderly so they can be motivated to live a higher quality by worshiping and getting closer to God.

CONCLUSION

Spiritual Strengthening is one of the most important things in building human quality because this dimension connects humans

¹⁴ Skills Provide Reinforcement. (2016).

https://sc.syekhnujati.ac.id/esscamp/files_dosen/modul/Pertemuan_4TA61_20236.pdf. Accessed 12

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¹⁵Muchlisin Riadi. *Reinforcement (reinforcement): Definition, Purpose, Principles, types*. <https://www.kajianpustaka.com/2021/04/penguatan-reinforcement-pengertian.html> di akses pada 12 Maret 2023

¹⁶ Riadi, Muchlisin, *Reinforcement (Rainforcement) Definition, Purpose, Principles, Types and Techniques. Literature Review, 21 April 2021*, <https://www.kajianpustaka.com/2021/04/penguatan-reinforcement-pengertian.html>

¹⁷Burhanuddin, Wordpress, "Skills to Give Reinforcement in Teaching and Learning Activities". <https://afidburhanuddin.wordpress.com/2017/07/14/keterampilan-memberi-penguatan-pada-kegiatan-belajar-mengajar/> accessed on 21 March 2023.

with their God. The spiritual aspect also allows the elderly to draw closer to God as a form of surrender to their current situation. Spiritual strengthening of the elderly can minimize the occurrence of depression in the elderly. Based on the existing theory, depression is one of the psychological problems experienced by the elderly. Therefore, the purpose of providing reinforcement methods is 1) to increase the spirit of life for the elderly 2) to develop and manage themselves 3) to direct good and positive ways of thinking. The methods and techniques that will be used in counseling the elderly are group reinforcement, namely giving reinforcement to all members of the group can be done continuously as is the case with giving reinforcement to individuals.

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